

" Growing children's speech in the process of introducing them to the environment and nature "

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Abstract: Enriching the child's speech through familiarization with the environment in the organization of the process of speech development in a preschool educational organization

Key words: Proverb, proverb, fairy tale, epic, observation, communicative orientation, social situation, emotional experiences, fun games , diction, speech, empathy, dialogue

the preschool educational institution is to form the correct oral speech of children as a result of acquiring the artistic language of their people. This general task consists of the following special tasks: education of sound culture of speech, enrichment, strengthening and activation of vocabulary, improvement of grammatical correctness of speech, formation of oral (dialogic) speech, development of fluent speech, education of interest in artistic words , preparation for teaching literacy. It is necessary to implement the development of children's speech on the basis of an appropriate program. In this program, the range of knowledge about the environment and the size of the vocabulary, speech skills and skills that should be formed in children at each age stage are determined, and it aims to educate certain qualities of the person (approachability, politeness, modesty). should be kept. The speech development program is based on scientific principles, and it is aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's personality with all its content. The speech development program is implemented in the forms of the child's activities such as study, play, work and household activities. In the context of public education, education is the leading means of forming a child's speech. Teaching the mother tongue is the process of developing the child's cognitive abilities in a planned, purposeful manner, acquiring the most basic knowledge of the world around them and mastering the appropriate vocabulary, and forming speech skills and abilities. The main form of education for preschool children is training. For didactic purposes, the following types of training can be distinguished: - training to introduce new material; - trainings related to strengthening knowledge, skills and abilities; - exercises related to generalization and systematization of knowledge; - final exercises or assessment (control) exercises. It is recommended to conduct exercises for the development of children's speech from 1 to 3 years old in the form of didactic games, fun games, and stage performances. They should be not only entertaining, but also educational. The development of children's speech between 3 and 5 years old should have an emotional tone. It is necessary to use exhibitionism, game methods and didactic games. Speech development activities for children aged 5 to 7 years have a specific task - that is, it aims to prepare children for schooling. During the training, the pedagogue should develop the ability to carry out educational activities in addition to speech tasks (being attentive, listening to the pedagogue's task, understanding it and carrying it out clearly, being able to think in front of a group of children, responding to a peer's response it also performs the function of being able to give a simple assessment , etc. Positive results can be achieved if the best qualities acquired by the child in the preschool educational institution are continued in the family environment, and the best qualities acquired in the family are applied in the preschool educational institution.

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Educators should not only see the positive results of their experience in family education, but also support it and, based on this, parents should focus on the tasks that have not yet been solved in child education. The head is the person responsible for planning, organizing and leading the above work. An annual plan for work with parents is drawn up. This plan will be discussed in the pedagogical council. The plan specifies general and group meetings, open days for parents, talks and consultations, organizing exhibitions and concerts in parenting organizations, as well as the times of these events and the persons responsible for them. . The topics and content of the work with parents are reflected in the educator-methodist's plan and the educator's calendar plan. A lot of work on working with parents is carried out by the educator - pedagogue, because he knows more than anyone about the changes taking place in the upbringing of children and is closely familiar with the life of children. He advises parents on what to pay more attention to in the education of children, such as preparation for school education, health care, proper organization of food and daily routine, etc. 2. Contents of the preschool educational institution's work in cooperation with parents. The headmaster, team of pedagogues and parents should actively participate in cooperation between educational institutions and schools. Only then can the expected results in child education be achieved. The following special forms of work are used in working with parents: interviews, consultations, visiting families, inviting some parents to the preschool, using special memorabilia and portable folders. The purpose of visiting the child's home is to learn about the family conditions, the child's behavioral interests in the family, to get to know the parents and family members, as well as to introduce the parents to the effective methods of child education, and to study and publicize the positive experience of the family in child education. The educator should go to the child's house not as an inspector, but as a friend, a helper in such a complex task as raising a child, and should treat family members with kindness and courtesy. Before every visit to each family, the educator should set a clear goal for himself, decide in advance what topic he will talk about. Questions to parents should be carefully thought out. The interview should be structured in such a way that the tutor and parents understand each other well, and there should be reliable communication between them. Before visiting the family, the educator should have certain ideas about this family (the character of the parents, family relations, the level of the child's development). In order to gain the respect and trust of the parents, the educator first learns the opinions and opinions of the parents about the positive qualities of the child and how to organize the life of the child at home, what can be read and told to him, the child's schedule, makes recommendations on the content and methods of educational work, such as involving him in family work, raising him in the spirit of respect for adults. Of course, the educator's work with the family takes into account the child's age, capabilities, and unique characteristics. The purpose and content of the visit to the family should be reflected in the educator's plan and report, as well as in his diary. The educator must visit each child's family at least twice a year. . The content of the work carried out with parents is varied, and it is necessary to discuss some issues together. For example: • the role of the family in raising children, the role of parents, laws on preparing children for school; • on the annual work plan of pre-school education institutions; • issues about the work of the parents' community are among them. Forms of work such as groups of parents and general meetings, consultations, conferences, parents' evenings for discussing this issue as a team are included in the forms of team work. Parents meeting. Parents of all groups of children, parents of parallel groups and parents of children of the same group can be invited to the meeting of parents. At the general meeting,

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parents will be introduced to the tasks of comprehensive development and upbringing of children of preschool age, plans for this year, activities of the parents' committee, best practices in family education. At the meeting, the headmaster or a Methodist educator will give a speech, parents will speak, and children will speak. These allow to identify achievements and shortcomings in educational work, strengthen family and public relations, increase the responsibility of parents for their child's education, and arouse interest in preschool educational institutions. At the meeting of parents in the group, the issues that are relevant for parents of children of this age are discussed. For example, if the topic of the general meeting is "The role of the family in providing moral education to children", then this topic will be complicated in the meeting held in the middle group, and the topics will be "Joint work of educational institutions and the family in raising diligence in children", "Education of respect for adults in children" and etc. can be. A lecture prepared for parents can be combined with children's work, a film on a related topic, and viewing slides. When using examples of children's life and activities, there should be more positive materials, while talking about negative facts, caution and decency should not be deviated from, and the names of those criticized should not be shown. After the meeting, critical comments can be delivered to parents through a private conversation, specific recommendations can be offered to eliminate mistakes and shortcomings in child education. At the end of the year gathering, parents are told about the educational work done during the year and the plans for the next year. At this meeting, active parents will also report, and a new active staff will be elected. Organization of parents' corner and exhibition. Parents' Corner is organized in order to introduce news and pedagogical issues related to parenting. They include books, articles, pictures, my child's work, types of baby food, my child's home and family agenda, reminders for parents, and announcements. The corner is changed from time to time depending on the educational task. Exhibitions organized for the promotion of pedagogical knowledge are often organized before parent conferences, meetings, and consultations. It contains laws and decisions on public education, diagrams showing the growth of the network of preschool educational institutions and the number of students in them, education and upbringing processes conducted with children, images depicting children's lives, a book and toys, my child's work takes place. Parents' corner is a demonstration method of work with the family, special attention should be paid to its tasteful decoration. In addition, parenting films are shown, which often lead to discussions that interest parents.

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